

HEAT TRANSFER COEFFICIENT DISTRIBUTION INSIDE AN AUTOCLAVE

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SUMMARY

All polymer matrix composite structures undergo a thermal cycle during the manufacturing process. In the vast majority of cases, heating and cooling is by convective heat transfer from a gas into the part and tool. Although numerical simulations of the thermal history evolution have been performed since the 1980s, there is still surprisingly little systematic understanding of what a desirable heat transfer coefficient should be, other than a general belief that a higher heat transfer coefficient is surely better. In this context, there has been some work on measuring heat transfer coefficients inside autoclaves, but again there are fewer systematic and complete studies than might be expected. The need for understanding heat transfer coefficients is even more acute in non-autoclave processes, such as oven curing, which are becoming more popular. Therefore, in this study we present preliminary results of a major systematic study of heat transfer in autoclaves (and ovens) using simple lumped mass calorimeters as well as more complicated plate calorimeters with measured thermal gradients.

Keywords: heat transfer, processing, manufacturing, autoclave, oven

INTRODUCTION

All polymer matrix composite structures are manufactured by having the part, and the tool on which is placed, subjected to a prescribed thermal history. This thermal history is critical in ensuring that the manufactured part has fully developed the mechanical and other properties on which the design is based. This is true for both thermoset and thermoplastic matrix composites; in the case of the former, for both resin-infused and prepreg systems. The thermal history is imparted to the part most often by heating and cooling the part and tool by convective heat transfer in an autoclave or oven. Currently, autoclave processing is the most widely used method for producing high quality composite structures in the aerospace industries, but there is increasing interest in oven curing materials.

Convective heat transfer is clearly a very well studied field of mechanical engineering, and there is a wealth of understanding and techniques for studying and characterizing heat transfer coefficients [eg 1-7]. Nevertheless, the determination of forced convective heat transfer in highly turbulent conditions is still fraught with difficulties. Most studies of autoclaves to date [5,7] assume, either explicitly or implicitly, that the airflow in the autoclave is fairly uniform. Additionally, they typically concentrate on the heat transfer from the bag-side of the part, and less so on the heat transfer through the sub-structure of the tool. In reality, autoclaves (and ovens) rarely have uniform gas flow fields. In fact it is very rare, perhaps unheard of, for autoclaves to have a specification with regard to flow uniformity, as opposed to the common requirement for temperature uniformity. The tooling is also very important: Airflow is disturbed under the tool and the resulting

asymmetry of heat transfer coefficients and the thermal mass of the tooling itself are very important parameters in determining the resulting thermal history.

The convective heat flux is described by the equation:

$$\dot{q} = hA(\Delta T_s) \quad (1)$$

where A is the surface area, ΔT_s is the difference in temperature between the solid surface and ambient surrounding fluid, and h is the convective heat transfer coefficient (HTC) [8]. Consequently, the heat transfer coefficient can be measured by:

$$h = \frac{\Delta Q}{A \cdot \Delta T_s \cdot \Delta t} \quad (2)$$

where ΔQ is heat input or heat lost, and Δt is the time period. The heat transfer coefficient in turn is a function of the gas properties, local gas velocity, and the geometrical features of the gas-structure interaction. Heat transfer coefficients in autoclaves are typically measured using lumped mass calorimeters [1,4,7] and it is generally accepted that in an autoclave the gas flow patterns can be quite complex, for both empty and loaded autoclaves. In principle, computational fluid dynamics analyses of the airflow in an autoclave can be performed, but there are relatively few examples in the open literature. Perhaps this is a reflection of the relative immaturity of process simulation as an industrial process design tool: there is still a significant lack of understanding on how a better knowledge of HTCs can lead to better manufacturing outcomes.

As an example, consider a 15 mm thick part made of AS4/8552 composite on a 15 mm thick Invar tool, subjected to a 2 °C/minute ramp to a hold temperature of 180 °C. A 0.7 mm thick compacted breather and vacuum bag is also included in the analysis. Typically, the maximum permissible temperature will be 185 °C, and thus the questions are: (a) how high should be the HTC in the autoclave generally, (b) how well should the air flow under the tool and (c) what should be the resulting local HTC under the tool? An intuitive response would be that a higher HTC should lead to a smaller exotherm. Simulation results for the mid-point thermal history from a simple 1D representation of this problem solved using the finite element process simulation code RAVEN [9] are shown in Figure 1, whilst the peak exotherm values are shown in tabular format in Table 1. The results are non-intuitive until explained: the highest symmetric HTC value of 300 W/m²K (a very high value highly unlikely to be attained in an autoclave) leads to the highest exotherm, whereas the lowest symmetric value of h=50 W/m²K leads to the lowest exotherm for symmetric heat transfer. The reason is that a higher HTC leads to a higher base temperature at the onset of reaction. Interestingly, the smallest exotherm occurs when the heat transfer under the tool is poor, leading to lagging temperatures in the tool. As a result, the initial heat-up is the slowest, but when the reaction sets off, the tool can quickly absorb the heat generated. In this case, the exotherm leads to an acceptable maximum temperature of 184.9 °C. We caution that there is no generality to this example, but it serves to illustrate the complex response of what appears to be a simple case.

Figure 1. Evaluation of thermal histories for a 15 mm thick AS4/8552 part on a 15 mm thick Invar tool using a 1D thermal simulation in RAVEN [9].

Table 1. Maximum temperatures taken from the results of Figure 1.

HTC Top (W/m ² K)	HTC Bottom (W/m ² K)	ΔT Exotherm (°C)
300	300	192.3
200	200	192.2
100	100	191.1
50	50	188.9
300	25	184.9

As part of our ongoing research into the development of best practices for cure cycle design, it has become clear that there is a need for inexpensive, simple, small and robust heat transfer measurement techniques. In this paper, we present preliminary results on lumped mass calorimeters similar in principle to those used previously [1,4,7] but of much smaller size, as well as more complex large calorimeters intended to measure top and bottom HTC values simultaneously.

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Two types of calorimeters were used in the experiments as shown in Figure 2.

1. Steel rods of length 75 mm and diameter 16 mm had two thermocouples embedded at the centreline of the rod. One additional thermocouple is used to measure local air temperature.
2. A steel plate of length 53 mm, width 30.5 mm and thickness 25 mm with seven thermocouples embedded through the thickness of the plate. Two additional thermocouples were placed on the top and bottom of the plate to measure local air temperature. The edges of the plate are heavily insulated to create a 1D heat transfer condition in the thickness direction.

Figure 2. Schematic of (a) the rod and (b) plate calorimeters.

Experimental Setup 1

The first experimental setup was designed to measure the overall HTC distribution inside the autoclave and its variation with pressure and temperature. The setup consisted of 10 rod calorimeters at various locations and 1 plate calorimeter centred inside the autoclave. Figure 3 shows the layout of the calorimeters and Figure 4 shows the temperature and pressure cycle used for the experiment.

Figure 3. Location of calorimeters in autoclave – Experimental setup 1. Note that Calorimeter 1 is at the inlet, which in this autoclave is under the floor (only).

Experimental Setup 2

The second experimental setup was designed to compare the measured HTCs from the rod calorimeters to the plate calorimeter and to check for any size effects on the measured HTCs. Six rod calorimeters and 1 plate calorimeter were placed inside the autoclave as shown in Figure 5. Three calorimeters were placed beneath the plate and three were placed above the plate. A single ramp and single hold cycle with 690 kPa (100 psig) autoclave pressure, shown in Figure 6, was used for experimental setup 2.

Figure 4. Temperature and pressure cycle for experimental setup 1.

Figure 5. Location of calorimeters in autoclave – Experimental setup 2.

CALCULATION OF HEAT TRANSFER COEFFICIENT

Following from Eqn (2) above, the heat input for a given time period can be calculated from:

$$\Delta Q = \int_v \rho C_p \Delta T dV \quad (3)$$

where ΔT is the increment of temperature over Δt .

If the rod calorimeter acts as a lumped mass (no temperature gradient in the rod), equation (2) can be simplified to:

$$\Delta Q = \rho C_p \Delta T V \quad (4)$$

And hence, the heat transfer coefficient is given by:

$$h = \frac{\rho C_p V \dot{T}}{A \Delta T_s} \quad (5)$$

Figure 6. Temperature and pressure cycle for experimental setup 2.

For the plate, if there is only 1D heat flow in the thickness direction, the heat input is given by:

$$\Delta Q = \int_{\text{surface}}^{\text{adiabatic}} \rho C_p A \Delta T dz \quad (6)$$

Where the adiabatic line is defined as the position where the temperature gradient is zero. The above integral can be performed using a simple rectangular integration rule if there are enough temperature points through the thickness [10]. Hence, the heat transfer coefficient is given by:

$$h = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \rho C_p L \Delta T_i \Delta \zeta_i}{\Delta T_s \Delta t} \quad (7)$$

where the subscript i is the measurement point of the thermocouples in the experiments ($i = 1$ is the surface and $i = n$ is the adiabatic line).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Experimental Setup 1

The HTC values throughout the autoclave varied from 60-200 W/m²K even though the largest temperature variation in the autoclave was only 4 °C. Figure 7 shows that the HTC was highest at Calorimeter 1 (175-200 W/m²K) where the high velocity hot air first enters the autoclave through an inlet at the bottom. As the air moves up the face of the autoclave door to Calorimeters 9 and 10 the HTC decreases slightly, to 140-190 W/m²K, but remains higher than elsewhere in the autoclave. The remaining rod calorimeters and the plate calorimeter, which are all at the lower part of the autoclave, show similar HTCs of 60-130 W/m²K.

Figure 7. HTC values at different locations throughout the autoclave.

The pattern of the HTC measurements suggests that the airflow comes out of the inlet under the floor, up and around the door, hugging the ceiling, and then to the outlet of the ceiling. A similar trend was observed in a preliminary CFD simulation of this autoclave, as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8. CFD simulation results of airflow overlaid with calorimeter locations [courtesy of Dr. Daan Maijer]

Table 2 shows the HTC variation with temperature and pressure at different stages of the autoclave cycle. The pattern of difference between calorimeters is maintained regardless of the temperature or pressure. For example, Calorimeter 9 is always higher than Calorimeter 10 and Calorimeter 5 is always higher than Calorimeter 2. This confirms that the airflow pattern is not changing with different temperatures and pressures.

Table 2. HTC variation at various stages of the temperature-pressure cycle.

Segment	Time (min)	Temp (°C)	Pres (psig)	HTC (W/m ² K)				
				1	2	5	9	10
Ramp 1	40	58	51	173	88	94	149	144
Ramp 1	45	71	51	181	82	88	153	147
Ramp 1	50	85	51	175	79	85	149	143
Ramp 2	120	132	101	186	104	108	178	154
Ramp 2	125	148	101	167	94	98	166	140
Ramp 2	130	159	101	170	91	96	164	139
Cool	185	122	1	47	42	46	59	61
Cool	190	100	1	47	37	37	48	42
Cool	195	84	1	43	34	39	56	60

If the gas can be assumed to behave as an ideal gas, and the air velocity is assumed constant, the effect of temperature and pressure on the HTC for fully developed turbulent flows can be estimated as [8]:

$$h \propto \left(\frac{P}{T} \right)^{\frac{4}{5}} \quad (8)$$

Figure 9 shows the ratio of measured HTCs compared to equation 8. The 1:1 relationship expected from equation 8 was roughly observed for Ramp 1 and Cool Down, but not Ramp 2. The cause for this discrepancy is that the autoclave fan appears to be unable to keep the air velocity constant as the autoclave pressure increases to 690 kPa (100 psig) (as shown by the lower HTC values seen with Calorimeter 1). In other words, as the gas density increases, the fan is not powerful enough.

Experimental Setup 2

Experimental Setup 2 was used to compare the size effect of the calorimeter on HTC measurement. According to the theory of thermal boundary layers [8], the HTC should decrease with increasing length of the calorimeter. Figure 10 shows the HTC values at the top and bottom of the plate using both types of calorimeters. There is no significant difference between the calculated HTC of the rod and plate calorimeters in this experiment. The reason for the lack of a size effect is likely that the calorimeters are sharing the same airflow as the plate. This suggests that the placement of small calorimeters on or below a tool will provide the correct local HTC value.

Figure 9. Variation of HTC with pressure and temperature as described by Eqn (8).

Figure 10. Comparison of HTC measurement from rod and plate calorimeters.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

Accurate knowledge of HTC values throughout an autoclave or oven, particularly above a part and under a tool, is needed for accurate prediction of the thermal history of a composite structure. The ability to measure HTCs simply and inexpensively but with acceptable accuracy, confidence and reliability is a necessary component of any

simulation aided process design workflow. We have presented preliminary results using two types of calorimeters, and it seems that the small rod calorimeters are promising options as a small and inexpensive method to measure HTC values.

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